

The Importance of the Role Destination Image, Tourist Motivation to Create Return Interest

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ABSTRACT

Objective study this is to describe the image of the destination, motivate tourists, and increase interest in the destination tour of Kediri Regency. Location study in tourist destinations in Kediri Regency. The data collection technique used is a questionnaire. Technique data analysis in the study uses engineering model analysis, descriptive statistics. The study found that affective, unique, and cognitive images determine destination images. Tourist motivation is determined by stress-busting / fun, novelty-seeking, achievement, and family oriented / education. Memorable tourism experience is determined by involvement, refreshment, hedonism, meaningfulness, culture and social interaction, knowledge, and novelty. The intention to revisit is determined by the willingness to invite, willingness to positive tale, willingness to prioritize the visiting destination, and willingness to visit again. The biggest contribution to the formation of intention to revisit is the willingness to invite reflected from the will to recommend to friends to visit Kediri. It is expected to support an effective and sustainable tourism development strategy for destinations that tour Kediri Regency.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Interest visit repeats in context tourist refers to the desire or motivation of somebody to return to a place the tour that ever they visited previously. Interest visits are important in the industry because they can create a stable income and increase reputation as an objective, interesting tour. Therefore, destination tourists often try to maintain and improve service quality and promote experience to increase interest in repeat visits. Interest in a visit is influenced by various factors, such as quality services and experiences, recommendations from people, satisfaction, and positive memories from previous visits, which can encourage someone to return.

The tourism industry often considers the intention to revisit. Because low intention to revisit a place can hurt profitability, the tourism industry is very competitive and makes it difficult for tourism managers to identify factors that influence visits. Based on prospective visitors, the experiences of experienced visitors can influence the decision to visit. Remember, industry tourists have a strong connection with other industries, such as flights, accommodation, transportation surfaces, water transportation, telecommunications, management attractions, providers of travel, manufacturers of craft handcrafted and designed

souvenirs for visitors, and related outlets (Ashoer et al., 2021).

Pratminingsih et al., (2014); East, (2019); Çevrimkaya & Zengin, (2023) stated that the first factor that influences the interest in revisiting is the destination image, that the destination image and satisfaction directly influence the interest in revisiting. The results of research by RG Nurazizah & Marhanah (2020) and Rosli et al., (2023) show that the destination image influences the interest to revisit directly or when mediated by satisfaction. Meanwhile, the research results of Indriani et al., (2021) show that destination image does not directly affect satisfaction and satisfaction does not mediate the influence of destination image on revisit interest.

Pratminingsih et al., (2014) and Thammadee, (2015) stated that motivation influences the interest in revisiting. The research results of Simpson et al., (2020) and He & Luo, (2020) showed the results of motivation positively and significantly influences the intention to revisit through tourist satisfaction. Meanwhile, other studies conducted by Chang et al., (2014) and Tysa & Dwita, (2022) shows that satisfaction influences the intention to revisit, while tourists' motivation to travel does not influence the intention to revisit.

Hu & Xu, (2021); Pai et al., (2020); Pai et al., (2021) put forward another opinion regarding the factors that also

influence the intention to revisit is experience, where experience has a significant effect on the intention to revisit. Other research conducted by Chou, (2013); Shahijan et al., (2018); Situmorang et al., (2020); Atmari & Putri, (2021), that satisfaction mediates the influence of experience on the intention to revisit. Meanwhile, research conducted by Tarmidi (2021) found different results, namely that experience did not significantly affect the interest in returning to visit.

In 2016, based on the RIPPDA (Regional Tourism Development Master Plan) document for Kediri Regency, there were approximately 54 tourist destinations/attractions, which continued to increase until 2021. Kediri Regency had 86 (eighty-six) tourist destinations/attractions managed by the district government, private sector, forestry, water services, and potential tourist attractions. Then, there was a significant decline in tourist visits for two years due to force majeure with the COVID-19 pandemic that hit the world, including the Kediri Regency.

There are so many tourist destinations in Kediri Regency, so researchers took 4 locations: the Mount Kelud tourist destination, the Besuki tourist area, the Sumber Podang tourist area, and the Simpang Lima Gumul tourist area. Based on data from the performance report of the Tourism Office 2022, these four locations are the largest contributors to Regional Original Income (PAD), so these destinations are the most in-demand for tourists to visit. Therefore, the researcher is interested in knowing more about the influence of the destination's image, motivation for travelers, and experiences of an impressive tour to interest visitors return through satisfaction tourists on tour Kediri Regency.

The desired goal obtained in the study is to describe the image of the destination, motivate tourists, experience a memorable tour, and satisfy tourist's interest in the destination tour Kediri Regency. Benefit this study can give benefits and uses that can be obtained. As for benefits obtained from the study among others: Contribution academic that results assessment scientific can be used For complete material reference for the researcher next one to take Topic about image destination, motivation tourists, experiences memorable tour, satisfaction tourists and interests visit return. Contribution practical that this study can be used as input for local tourism area managers in carrying out regular maintenance and care and for the local government to explore local tourism potential that can be utilized by the community further.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Destination Image

Wibowo et al., (2016) define destination image as a decision of a journey from individual thoughts in the form of knowledge, feelings, and perceptions to the overall thought of the purpose of the experience based on the level of visitor satisfaction with the destination visited. The image of a

destination by Stylos et al., (2016) is interpreted as a series of impressions, ideas, hopes, and emotional thoughts that a person has from a predetermined destination. From the description above, the destination image is the perception and emotional thoughts that tourists have from a tourist destination.

Tocquer & Zins, (2004) grouped images into 4 stages: Vague and unrealistic image, formed before tourists travel from advertising, education, and word of mouth. Distortion of the image when tourists decide to go on vacation by choosing the time, destination, and type of tourism product. Improve the image when tourists have a vacation experience. The resulting image, this stage, refers to memories of traveling. Rajesh, (2013) stated that the image of a particular tourist destination can be influenced by infrastructure facilities, natural attractions, historical and cultural attractions, safety and cleanliness of the tourist destination, friendliness of residents, affordability, and costs incurred to pay for tourism services.

2.2 Tourist Motivation

Esichaikul, R. (2012), “*Motivation is a state of need or a condition that drives an individual toward certain types of action that are seen as likely to bring satisfaction*”, which means that motivation is a condition that drives someone to do something that will make him happy. Khan et al., (2019) define tourist motivation as an individual's psychological state that arises due to the need to take action. Tourist motivation, such as expectations and attitudes, can influence tourist travel to certain destinations, influencing tourist loyalty (Cohen & Fulkerson, 2014).

2.3 Interest in Returning

According to Zhang et al., (2018), interest in visit return is the behavior of visitors, where visitors respond positively to the place that was visited and push to visit further. Visitation back to the destination tour's experience directly strengthens a visit (Zhang et al., 2018). According to Ting & Thurasamy (2016), the power of a good tour can cause a positive impression on visitors that brings up interest in return visits, on the other hand, time.

Zeithaml (2010) explains that revisit intention can be identified through several indicators, namely, willingness to visit or to visit repeatedly. Willingness to invite or willingness to invite and invite others to visit. Willingness to tell a positive tale or willingness to tell and spread an experience destination tour. Willingness to prioritize the visiting destination or willingness to make objective destination tour a priority.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses an approach study, with design study explanatory research, to describe pattern descriptions of research variables. The location of this study is a tourist destination in Kediri Regency. Data was collected using a questionnaire, with tourists or visitors to tourist attractions as

respondents. The data analysis technique used is descriptive analysis.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Affective, unique, and cognitive images indicate the destination image. Study This discloses that related activities with affective image among other tourists feel like after coming on holiday to destination tourism in the district, Kediri feels comfortable during the moment of visit to destination tourism. Activities related to unique image consist of destination tourism in the district Kediri, which has a unique icon in the form of crater child mountains and waterfalls, and there is a place for camping. Activities related to cognitive image, among other destination tours, can be accessed using general transportation and attractions tourism in destination tours. There are enough various. Description results in image destination consisting of affective, unique, and cognitive images in line with indicators developed by Qu et al. (2011) and Stylos et al., (2016). The biggest contribution to the formation image destination is a unique image reflected from the statement, with a unique icon in the form of crater child mountains and waterfalls. The crater is often considered a "child mountain" because its location is lower and larger than the crater, but it still offers a spectacular and interesting landscape. The color of the crater water varies due to the content of sulfur or other minerals that add power to pull it. Visit crater child mountain, which usually involves challenging trekking activities, where tourists can enjoy viewing stunning nature along the way of track climbing. Cool mountain air and calm atmosphere give deep experiences, especially when reaching the peak and seeing a direct crater. While related to the waterfall, travelers can usually enjoy the beauty of the waterfall by walking through the path that has been provided. Several waterfalls allow visitors to swim or soak their feet in the pool, allowing them to experience relaxation and freshness. The atmosphere, the surrounding nature, and the sound of falling water add comfort and peace during the visit. Combining both tourist icons, this crater-child mountain, with its amazing landscape and volcanic and enchanting waterfalls, offers an experienced tour of complete nature, combining adventure and relaxation. Destinations like this are very suitable for lovers of nature who seek beauty, unique nature, and challenges in nature-free.

Motivation travelers indicated stress-busting / fun, novelty-seeking, achievement, and family-oriented / education. Activity-related stress-busting / fun consists of travelers doing activity traveling to release fatigue, and tourists spend time traveling with friends. Activities related to novelty seeking consist of travelers visiting to enjoy beautiful views and historical places. Activities related to achievement consist of travelers doing journey tours as an award to themselves alone and enjoying package tours offered. Activities related to family-oriented / education consist of travelers using up time with family and doing

activities traveling with the closest people. Description motivates tourists by focusing on stress-busting / fun, novelty-seeking, achievement, and family oriented / education, which align with developed indicators (Siri et al., 2012). The biggest contribution to form motivation travelers is stress-busting / fun, reflected in the statement Traveling For letting go of tiredness. Traveling to let go of fatigue is a purposeful activity to eliminate fatigue, stress, and boredom from daily routine. Travel This usually focuses on relaxation, refreshment thoughts, and filling return energy with a method to enjoy a different atmosphere from daily life by traveling to a natural destination like mountains, beaches, or lakes, offering a calm and distant atmosphere from the noisy city. Fresh air, views of vast green, and nature like the sound of trickling water or chirping birds can help remove stress and bring a calm mind. Travel naturally allows travelers to rest for a moment, enjoy the beauty of nature, and find it hard to find peace in life daily.

Interest in visit return indicated willingness to invite, willingness to positive tale, willingness to place the visiting destination in priority, and willingness to visit again. Activity-related willingness to invite consists of travelers recommending friends to visit Kediri, and tourists will invite colleagues to visit Kediri. Activities related to willingness to positive tale consist of being a tourist telling experience tourism in Kediri, and tourists will share their experiences traveling with others. Activities related to willingness to place the visiting destination in priority consist of travelers interested. For come again on another day and time holiday, travelers will visit again to Kediri. Activities related to willingness to visit again consist of the traveler returning and traveling again and the affordable distance from the house to the destination tour.

Description results in interest in visiting back consisting of willingness to invite, willingness to positive tale, willingness to place the visiting destination in priority, and willingness to visit again in line with developed indicators (Zeithaml, 2010). The contribution the biggest former interest in visit return is a willingness to invite, which is reflected in the statement that will recommend to friend for a visit to destination tourism. When recommending destination tourism, people usually emphasize what makes the place special and different from others. For example, they could mention the beautiful views of nature, the uniqueness of culture, or exciting activities. Power pull this is why the place is properly visited and will give a satisfying experience. Sometimes, recommendations for destination tourism are also followed with an invitation to visit together another time, build togetherness and opportunity, and create memories together.

5. CONCLUSION

Affective, unique, and cognitive images determine the destination image. Uniqueness matters; most image destinations reflect a unique tourist icon in crater child

mountains and waterfalls. Motivation is determined by stress-busting / fun, novelty-seeking, achievement, and family orientation/education. The most appreciated contribution is stress-busting/fun reflected from traveling to release fatigue. Interest in a visit return is determined by willingness to invite, willingness to tell a positive story, willingness to prioritize the visiting destination, and willingness to visit again. The biggest contribution to the formation of interest in visit return is the willingness to invite, as reflected in the recommendation to friends to visit Kediri. With various research and suggestions said, it is expected that it can produce a better understanding of factors that influence interest in returning to destination tourism in Kediri Regency so that it can support the development strategy of effective and sustainable tourism.

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